

THE IMPORTANCE OF DIGITAL TOOLS IN THE CLASSROOM

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As today's young learners are digital native, traditional teaching methods are not popular any more. It is very hard to engage students by using hand out and text books. Arno Macia (2012) says that everyone is the independent user of IT and in every field it has got very significant role in the society. Like other fields, in education and teaching teachers can not organize their lessons without technologies. Since all the students are from Generation Z and they are digital native students for each lesson I have to prepare tasks online. Sometimes checking students vocabulary is also takes more time and many students think that is very time consuming and boring process. That is why for ice breaker activity, I mostly use online games from " Bamboozle" or Kahoot" or Quizzex.com". According to Kirovska (2017) using technologies helps teacher to make more interesting lesson atmosphere.

As learning center provides projector I always use presentations for my students. Canva is the best website for me. Firstly, it is totally free and it offers many free and interesting emojis, videos and pictures. That is why, I do not need to search some picture or graphics from Google.

Moreover, we cannot imagine our lessons without CALL activities. Not only universities but also at schools or Learning Centers as well teachers are using them. They make our lessons much more interesting and understandable. Daa Haan (2011) said that today's modern students are very engaged to digital tools and they are active users of IT. Because of these reasons, we have to use them in our lessons.

Although my students are very active in Reading and Listening tasks and their mock results are also very good in exams, their speaking and writing results are not good enough. The main reason of it is they do not use Advanced Grammar in their written speeches or essays. Although in the classroom they seem to understand everything, they cannot use them in real life. I have used many ways and games to fix this problem. I have chosen Conjunctions theme as an assignment.

There are some reasons why I have created these game is Bamboozle is totally free for users and signing up to the website and creating new games is also easy. When it comes to other websites, they always have problems with sharing codes or sometimes some games or tasks will be removed without any reason. Secondly, other sites provide gifs, emojis, texts and other good visuals for only premium users or least users have to buy monthly accounts. But this site is totally different.

Thirdly, by using its own library, we are able to add videos or background picture for the question. Last but not least we can write explanations to the answer part. If teachers have kids students they can add music for kids. As more than 1 million English teachers are using it, we are able to use other teachers' work to learn new things or to develop our own making game styles.

In conclusion, these game helps them to remember confusing rules in grammar very well. After showing the answer, I always give another examples and explanation. I have

notices good results and active grammar in my students essays after using this game. Short descriptions and examples help them to use them actively in their written exercises.

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